

USE OF MODERN METHODS IN TEACHING MOTHER LANGUAGE LESSONS.

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Abstract: Today's intense era requires every person to diligently study, learn science and craft from childhood. Based on this demand, a unique education system was created in our country: the Law "On Education" and the "National Program of Personnel Training" were adopted. Among other areas of education, mother tongue education has a special place in them. This article provides information about the teaching methodology of mother tongue science.

Key words: Methodology, Cacography, paronymous words, communication, pedagogy.

The mother tongue teaches the student to think independently, to fully express his thoughts orally and in writing. The student's level of literacy, his place in social life is built on the basis of knowledge and skills acquired from his mother tongue. It is known that each national language, in addition to adequately reflecting the material world, also fully expresses the spiritual world, its sorrows and joys. A person has the opportunity to express his attitude towards everything, and this opportunity is always revealed through certain forms of language.

Kacography, as one of the interactive methods, helps students to think independently, compare things with each other, search, find a solution to a problem, and most importantly, draw the necessary conclusions on certain topics based on the knowledge and skills acquired in native language classes. Dispels apathy and indifference in students, encourages courage and creativity, eliminates negative characteristics such as muteness, subordination, and inactivity. The cacography method is especially effective in passing practical lessons related to phonetics, graphics, orthography, lexicon and morphology. For example, it is appropriate to use different tasks in "Consolidation Lessons" or "Revision Lessons" after students have been given enough information about vowels and consonants. The main focus is on the difference between spoken and written words. It is known from experience that most of the students do not master the spelling rules thoroughly in their mother tongue classes. They get

used to writing the words as they are said. Also, dialectal errors in the students' speech affect their literacy. This gradually causes their literacy level to freeze, and words are regularly misspelled.

For example, in the oral speech of the students, words such as price, spring, with, star, theater, question, order, prosperity, pearl, Saturday, responsible, river are used as boho, spring, blan, star, theater, question, Ordin, obot, marvarit, shamba, masul, दौरا, and writing mistakes on this basis are common. This shows that they have sufficient knowledge and skills in the native language lessons on spelling of vowels and consonants. In order to prevent such errors, after passing the relevant theoretical information on the "Spelling of Certain Vowels and Consonants" in the "Rules of Spelling of the Uzbek Language", the following task will be given: Read the words, find the places where they are written incorrectly, correct them according to the spelling rules of the Uzbek language and copy and write them in your notebook. Bugalter, khayal, khayoy, holal, momila, qiqiq, rektir, conference, computer, maylis, etc. Correct spelling: accountant, imagination, modesty, honest, dealing, honest, law, rector, conference, computer, meeting. The following results can be achieved by completing such tasks in the cacographic direction:

- The relationship between the student and the teacher is strengthened;
- Pupils try to remember and recall the knowledge and skills acquired in the mother tongue;
- Compares and contrasts materials;
- Draws conclusions, strengthens orthographic knowledge.

The cacography method is especially effective in teaching the spelling of consonants that are often used instead of one, such as h - x, b - p, d - t, z - s. In this case, it is effective to use tools such as showing students the wrongly written words through slides, deliberately writing mistakes on the class board, using handouts with wrongly written words. For example: Identify the misspelled words, correct them according to the spelling rules and copy and write them in your notebook. Orombakhsh, reserve, desire, state of affairs, betrayal, sincerity, all, all, India, behavior, dream Correct spelling: orombakhsh, reserve, desire, situation, betrayal, sincerity, various, all, india, behavior, fantasy. The cacography method is also useful in passing topics related to lexicology. In the text, dars-darz, bob-bop, mart-mard, kasr-kasr, karam-karam, halak-halak, kaft-kift, asl-asil, asr-asir, end-end-end, chog are distinguished by one sound. Spelling paronyms like -chok-choh and asking students to correct them will

reinforce their knowledge. Find the misspelled passwords, correct them according to the spelling rules and copy them into your notebook.

Organizing meetings with experienced experts in the field of information and communication technologies who are masters of their profession, talking about them to students and answering questions by giving real examples. For this, he only advises on the need to read and study. Organizing meetings and discussions with such qualified specialists also increases students' interest in science. It is necessary to strengthen the desire of parents to raise their child to be a highly spiritual, educated and perfect person. At the Lyceum, parents are regularly communicated with and work with them in a relaxed manner. If the child's ability is not created together, this ability may slowly fade and disappear, and this may affect the child's choice of profession. information about negative effects is given. It is desirable to use more conference methods of educational technology. This method is carried out between parallel groups. Groups send questions to each other. The student who asked the question appears on the screen and tells the question to the students of the parallel group. Pupils sitting in class will answer. They get 5 points for the correct answer. Group scores are calculated during the semester and the most active group is determined at the end of the semester. This method encourages students to search, become fluent in their speech, and be able to use information and communication technologies effectively. Modern information and communication technologies have created a wide opportunity to develop new forms and methods of teaching. At the same time, the problem of in-depth teaching of information and communication technologies, students' acceptance, processing and independent work of a large amount of information is emerging. Many students who come from school to lyceum do not have enough skills to think and work independently. Some have very little interest in learning. Capable, inquisitive and creative children will receive in-depth lessons in the field of information and communication technologies that they are interested in.

In short, the quality and effectiveness of the lesson depends on the teacher's thorough preparation. In this, the design of lesson development in accordance with the modern technologies has a special place. In the field of education, the use of pedagogical and information-communication technologies, Internet information and educational resources, and the conference method will effectively help students to acquire knowledge at a high level and create an opportunity for them to become qualified specialists in the future.

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